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Article *in* Sustainable Development - January 2021

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Renewable energy public–private partnerships in developing countries: Determinants of private investment

Abstract:

In this research, we study, for the first time, the determinants of private investment participation in public–private partnership (PPPs) projects in renewable energies. We analyse a broad sample formed by 1,371 PPPs from 63 developing countries in the period 1997–2016. Using a Tobit estimation technique, our findings reveal that PPPs that are smaller, younger, where the private partner takes more responsibilities, and the prime revenue source comes from the electricity consumers' payments, show a greater degree of private investors' participation. In addition, better institutional and economic environments impact positively on the attractiveness of private investment. Other interesting findings are that the support of multilateral development banks (MDBs) positively affects the participation of private investors in renewable energy PPPs, and this becomes more important when the institutional and economic frameworks are weaker. [The article sheds light for practitioners and policy makers on promoting actions that reinforce the determinants that positively affect private participation. In this way, government actions that promote the institutional financing of third parties, as well as improvements to their institutions and economic environment, enable efforts to be prioritised due to the positive impact it has on private participation. Similarly, good indicators of these factors allow private investors to select projects that will be more successful.](#)

Keywords: Developing countries; Economic framework; Institutional framework; Multilateral Development Banks; Public–Private Partnerships (PPPs); Renewable energies.

1. Introduction

The thirteenth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG)¹ is '*to take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts*'. Nowadays, global warming is one of the most serious threats to our planet. The levels of CO₂ (carbon dioxide) and other greenhouse gases (GHG) in the atmosphere reached new record highs in 2019, according to United Nations (UN) estimations. Thus, mitigation measures are urgently required, otherwise the world's average surface temperature might rise by more than 3 degrees centigrade over this century. In addition, the consequences of global warming could be especially harmful in developing countries. Tol (2018) explains the three main reasons why these countries could be more vulnerable to temperature rise: (i) developing countries are more exposed to weather events due to the relevance of agriculture and water resources in their economy; (ii) these countries are usually located in hotter places meaning that their ecosystems are closer to their biophysical upper limits. Also, there are no examples of human behaviour and technologies managing temperature rises in these areas, that is, (Tol, 2018, p. 10) '*if the hottest places on the planet become even hotter, there are no existing examples to learn from; new technologies will have to be developed and behavior will have to be adjusted by trial and error*'; and iii) these countries have shown a limited capacity to adapt due to their lack of technology.

One of the main sources of CO₂ and other GHG emissions is the energy industry. More specifically, according to the last report of the IEA (International Energy Agency)², this industry is responsible for around 66% of total GHG emissions and more than 80% of CO₂ emissions. Within the energy industry, the electricity output from fossil fuels represented around 65% of emissions in 2017. Thus, the fostering of renewable energies, especially in developing countries, turns up as a key tool to hamper temperature rise and to promote the transition towards a low-carbon economic model. In this way, the seventh SDG established by the UN aims to '*ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy*'. More specifically, target 7.B states the following targets: '*By 2030, expand infrastructure and*

¹ <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/>

² CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion highlights 2019, available at: <https://webstore.iea.org/co2-emissions-from-fuel-combustion-2019-highlights>

upgrade technology for supplying modern and sustainable energy services for all in developing countries, in particular least developed countries, small island developing States, and land-locked developing countries, in accordance with their respective programmes of support'.

In this context, public–private partnerships (PPPs) constitute an important mechanism to achieve this target. Nowadays, PPPs are broadly used to deliver public infrastructure services, especially in developing countries (Ragosa & Warren, 2019). Chauhan and Marisetty (2019) highlight that PPPs are present in more than 134 developing countries, contributing to 15–20% of their total infrastructure investment. Electricity is not an exception. In the last decades, the delivery of electricity services has been usually performed through PPPs around the world (Sovacool, 2013). PPPs are defined by the Green Paper of European Commission (2004) as *'forms of cooperation between public authorities and the world of business which aim to ensure the funding, construction, renovation, management or maintenance of an infrastructure or the provision of a service'*. The main features of these agreements are their relatively long duration, the involvement of the private partner in the funding of the project and other stages (design, completion, implementation, etc.), and the share of risks between the public and private partners (Green Paper of European Commission, 2004, p. 3).

Sovacool (2013) explains that the excessive public debt and the consequent budgetary constraints faced by many countries after the economic crisis of the late 1970s and early 1980s, led those countries to abandon the traditional model of public procurement for electricity services and to adopt new ownership and procurement formulas. More specifically, these new formulas aimed to attract private money for funding electricity services' expansion. In fact, Sun et al. (2020) explain that the main barrier to the development of green projects is the difficulty in accessing financial resources since these projects are capital-intensive and suffer from several risks and a low rate of return compared to fossil fuel projects. In this way, the attraction of private investment could constitute a critical factor to promote renewable energies in developing countries through PPP projects. Thus, in this research, we analyse for the first time to the best of our knowledge, the factors that determine the degree of private participation in renewable energy PPPs in different types of renewable energies (enhanced geothermal, hydrothermal, waste-to-energy, wind, solar photovoltaic,

concentrated solar power, and biomass) for a broad sample formed by 1,371 projects, deployed in 63 developing countries in the period 1997–2016. In particular, we study the impact of the main characteristics of the projects, the institutional and economic environments where the PPPs are performed, and the support of multilateral development banks.

For this purpose, the paper is structured as follows: the second section is comprised of the literature review and establishes the research hypotheses (RH); the third section describes the data and methods used; the fourth section reports the main empirical findings and contains the discussion; the fifth section is comprised of the conclusions, limitations, and avenues for further research.

2. Literature review and research hypotheses

2.1. Literature Review

The Transaction Cost Theory (Williamson, 1979) is widely used to explain private participation in PPPs (Albalade et al., 2014; Basílio, 2017; Wang et al., 2018). The theory makes it possible to relate the degree of risk that the private agent would assume depending on the future benefits of accepting it (Fleta-Asín et al., 2020). Both extremes – risks that may entail costs and benefits of assuming them – in turn depend both on the characteristics of the transaction (Williamson, 1979), as well as the environment where it takes place (Fleta-Asín & Muñoz, 2020; Wang et al. 2019). Thus, it is generally believed that the lower the costs of participating, the higher the private participation with the public sector (Albalade et al., 2014; Wang et al. 2018,). For this reason, PPPs where for example the costs are reduced because of institutional financial support (Basílio, 2014), favourable specific regulations (Fleta-Asín & Muñoz, 2020), or the existence of local sponsors who know the market (Jiménez et al., 2017), may promote private participation.

In addition, the Principal-Agent Theory or Agency Theory, is also used to analyse the participation of the private sector, since the public part must establish mechanisms that not only facilitate the attraction of the private investor, but also correct the problems of adverse selection and the moral hazard of the potential private partner (Fleta-Asín & Muñoz, 2017; Percoco, 2014; Wang et al., 2018). Thus, addressing these problems may encourage the participation of the right private partner since their resolution can decrease opportunistic

behaviour. For this reason, the *ex-ante* creation of contracts awarded by competitive methods, for example, may reduce adverse selection (Wang et al., 2018), while other mechanisms such as the contractual form of collaboration can mitigate both *ex-ante* adverse selection, as well as *ex-dure* and *ex-post* moral hazard (Fleta-Asín et al. 2020).

On the other hand, most previous research about renewable energy PPPs focus on specific areas through case studies in specific locations. Some research focusses on southern Europe, such as a review of the methodology of implementing PPPs for the production of thermal and electrical power from biomass residues in agro-energy districts in rural areas of Greece and Italy (Manos et al., 2014); the role of PPPs in the diffusion of wind power in Spain (Dinica, 2008); a study of the impact of tourism in waste-to-energy utilities managed through PPPs agreements in Mallorca (Spain) (Arbulú et al., 2017); or the case of wind power generation through PPPs' agreements in Portugal (Martins et al., 2011). Other studies examine experiences in Asia, analysing PPPs in waste-to-energy utilities in the Philippines and India (Forsyth, 2005); or in Africa describing the case of the joint-stock company NEAL, the first Algerian PPP which develops projects in the production of electricity from renewable energies (thermal solar, photovoltaic solar, wind, geothermic, and biomass) (Stambouli, 2011). Another body of papers analyse experiences in a set of countries located on different continents. Thus, Rajpurkar (2015) identifies best practices in PPPs in renewable energies by performing a detailed analysis of two cases, the Renewable Energy Independent Power Procurement Program (REIPPP) of South Africa and the solar energy programmes implemented in the state of Gujarat, India. Cedrick and Long (2017) review the positive externalities that have triggered the rise of renewable energy PPPs and analyse some successful experiences from twelve countries to identify the key factors that moderate the risks related to renewable energy projects. Finally, Vagliasindi (2013) performs several case studies of PPPs in renewable energies in China, Brazil, Peru, and Mexico.

The analysis of some cases reveals two main aspects: high up-front investment and technology innovation feature renewable energy projects (Cedrick & Long, 2017), which become especially important in developing economies because of the lack of them (Ragosa & Warren, 2019; Sun et al., 2020). This situation can be mitigated through PPPs, since this procurement formula would allow the attraction of private money for funding electricity

services' expansion and the harnessing of the skills and technology innovation of the private sector (European Commission, 2004; Sun et al., 2020). Given its importance, previous academic literature has analysed the determinants of the private investment attraction in PPPs from other sectors. Thus, Percoco (2014) studies this topic for transport infrastructure PPPs and observes that a better institutional framework benefits private participation. Osei-Kyei and Chan (2017), using a survey questionnaire, observe that a positive political, legal, and social framework constitute key factors to attract private investors to PPPs in developing countries. Wang et al. (2018) analyse the impact of different contract features in attracting private participation for a sample of Chinese PPPs encompassing projects from different sectors (energy, transport, water sewerage, and information technology communication [ICTs] sectors). Wang et al. (2019) identify the risk allocation and the institutional environment as relevant factors for private participation in PPPs from different countries; they also extend their previous research by studying the effect of government support programmes (Wang et al., 2019b). Finally, Chen et al. (2020) explore the determinants of the private share in sports and leisure characteristics town PPPs in China³.

2.2. Research Hypotheses

To analyse the determinants of private investment in renewable energy PPPs in developing countries, we consider factors at the project level and the host country level. At the project level, we examine the next dimensions: the size, age, and type of PPP, the contract awarding method, the prime source of revenues, and the participation of local private sponsors.

The size of the PPP has been used in previous literature as a proxy of the complexity of the project (see Jimenez et al. 2017 or Wang et al. 2018, among others). More complex projects are related to higher transaction costs (Williamson, 1979) which could prevent private investors in engaging in PPP projects. Albalade et al. (2015) explain that the efficiency gains leading to cost reductions thanks to the involvement of private companies in public procurement diminish with transaction costs. When transaction costs are high '*smaller efficiency gains from private participation may be expected in such cases, which helps explain why governments choose limited private involvement in those project types*' (Albalade

³ Chen et al. (2020) explain that (p. 1) "*The Sports and Leisure Characteristic Town (SLCT) has become a reasonable strategy for enhancing the sustainability of new urbanization processes in rural China*".

et al., 2015, p. 94). PPP's complexity also impacts its performance. Jimenez et al. (2017) find that larger projects show a greater likelihood of failure. Thus, more complex projects could be less attractive to private companies. Therefore, our first research hypothesis (RH1) is as follows:

RH1: The size of the project negatively impacts the involvement of private investors in renewable energy PPPs.

The age of the project allows us to detect differences between projects deployed at different times. Renewable energies have substantially evolved. Two decades ago, the existing technology made it expensive and less competitive to generate electricity from renewable energies in comparison with carbon-intensive sources, making these projects less attractive for private investors (Sun et al., 2020). For example, Ragosa and Warren (2019) point out that in the UK, *'the costs for future offshore wind capacity reduced by 47.2% between the 2015 and 2017 auction rounds, the costs of onshore wind by 50% since 2009 and those of solar cells by 80% since 2008'* (Ragosa & Warren, 2019, p. 854). Zhang et al. (2013) point out that *'the improved competitiveness and capabilities of the manufacturers of renewable energy equipment, components and parts result in price reduction of wind turbines that leads in turn to lower costs for the installation and generation of wind power'* (Zhang et al., 2013, p. 343). Moreover, the adoption of more restrictive GHG emissions legislation, the setting of policies and tax incentives in favour of renewable energies, and the growing taxes imposed on pollution in many developing countries in the last years have provoked that renewable energy technologies have become more attractive from a financial point of view over time. It is not an aim in this article to carry out an analysis of green legislation in developing countries, but we can find interesting research in the literature on this issue. For example, Liu et al. (2017) explain the pro-environmental regulation and legislation amended by the Chinese government in the first decade of the 21st century. Thus, we find the *'Cleaner Production Promotion Law'* in 2003, the *'Law on Pollution Prevention and Control of Solid Waste'* amended in 2005, or the *'Circular Economy Promotion Law'*, approved in 2008. Carfora et al. (2018) perform interesting research on the determinants of the choice of energy policy setting in favour of renewable energy sources in both developed and developing countries. Washburn and Pablo-Romero (2019) study the measures adopted to promote

renewable energy for electricity generation in the eighteen Latin American countries that signed the Paris Agreement. Thus, we could expect that private investors have a greater share in most recent PPPs in comparison to those projects deployed earlier.

RH2: The age of the project impacts negatively the involvement of private investors in renewable energy PPPs.

PPPs are not a homogenous mechanism of project governance; different types exist with different responsibilities assumed by public and private partners (Fleta-Asín et al., 2020). For example, among other types of PPPs the World Bank defines Brownfield and Greenfield projects. Whereas in Greenfield projects the private partner usually assumes the responsibilities of building and operating a new facility for the period specified in the project contract, in Brownfield projects the private entity does not have the responsibility to build a new facility but it uses, rehabilitates, improves, or expands an existing asset. PPPs' contracts are incomplete and extend for long periods. In this vein, Hart et al. (1997) explain that the residual control rights over the assets to procure the service constitute a key driver of agents' incentives. If private investors possess greater residual control rights, they will have incentives to involve more in PPPs since *'Controlling rights over PPP projects allows the private sector to operate the facility for a longer time period and under more favourable conditions'* (Wang et al., 2018, p. 592). Thus, we could expect that PPP types in which the private partner takes more responsibilities, will be positively related to the degree of participation of the private sector.

RH3: Renewable energy PPPs' contracts in which the private sector takes more responsibilities are positively related to the degree of participation of the private sector.

Different procedures exist to select the private partner in a PPP contract. The main difference between these methods is whether they are based on competitive bidding or direct negotiation. Kaminsky (2017) explains that the optimal PPP award method could depend on project features and ownership requirements. Thus, competitive bidding methods would be optimal when the public sector party aims to select the private contractor by procuring a specific facility at the lowest price, whereas other methods based on direct negotiation could: lead to a decreased project duration, provide flexibility for changes, reduce adversarial relationships between the partners, and enlarge the scope of activities in which the private

contractor can be involved in – among other things – design and funding (Gordon, 1994). On the other hand, Wang et al. (2018) explain that competitive tendering attracts more efficient companies due to the transparency of these methods. These authors point out that the efficiency gains from the competitive tendering process will attract private investment. Thus, we propose the next research hypothesis:

RH4: Renewable energy PPPs' contracts awarded by competitive methods are positively related to the degree of participation of the private sector.

The private investor engaged in a renewable PPP project seeks a profit. Thus, another PPP feature that could shape the degree of private investor involvement would be the main source of revenues in the project. Different alternatives exist. In the sample analysed, most of the PPPs (around 73%) present a purchase agreement alternative as a main revenue source, in which the public partner agrees to purchase electricity from the private partner for some time. As Kaminsky (2017) points out, under purchase agreements, the private partner guarantees a revenue stream from the public sector. On the other hand, in fewer cases in our sample (around 12%⁴), the fees paid by electricity consumers (both the retail and wholesale markets) constitute the PPPs' prime revenue source. Private companies would be presented with more incentives to be competitive if their revenues depended on market demand than if they had a guaranteed stream of revenues from the public sector. Thus, if efficiency gains lead to a greater private involvement, as Wang et al. (2018) suggest for the PPP award method, we could expect the same regarding the main source of revenues. We propose the next research hypothesis:

RH5: When the main source of revenues in renewable energy PPPs depends on consumer demand, private involvement is greater.

The participation of private local sponsors could benefit PPPs' success. For example, Jimenez et al. (2017) explain that the involvement of local sponsors moderates the negative effect of corruption on PPPs' performance. Local sponsors know the host country's idiosyncrasies better and can help foreign private partners to mitigate the liabilities that suffer when operating in new markets. Fleta-Asín and Muñoz (2020) find that the presence of local

⁴ In the remaining PPPs, the label allocated to the prime revenue source is 'other'.

sponsors raises the PPPs' likelihood of success. Thus, the presence of local investors could encourage the involvement of private investors in renewable energy PPPs. Thus, our sixth research hypothesis is as follows:

RH6: Renewable energy PPPs in which local sponsors participate are positively related to the degree of participation of the private sector.

Previous literature has shown that PPPs' success will depend not only on the projects' features but also the environments where they are carried out (see among others, Fleta-Asín & Muñoz, 2020). At the country level, we consider the size of the country (judged by its GDP), the institutional framework (according to World Bank Governance Indicators, WGI), and the economic environment (according to Heritage Foundation Indicators). The size of the country could impact private participation in renewable energies projects. High GDP countries could present more demand for electricity services to maintain or increase their production making less likely the incidence of risk due to lack of demand. As Yehoue et al. (2006) point out, the profitability of PPP projects is a relevant factor for attracting private sector partners, and infrastructure projects are generally characterised by high upfront costs and often need time to generate revenues, and consequently, the commercial risk of such projects is high. This means that demand for the services to be delivered and the size of the market constitute key drivers of private sector participation in PPPs (Yu et al., 2018). Moreover, the institutional and economic environments could foster or hinder private sector engagement in PPPs. Yehoue et al. (2006) find that in developing economies, the macroeconomic stability, the quality of institutions, the control of corruption, and an independent judicial system explain a higher use of PPPs. Similar studies find that better institutions are positively related to the adoption of PPP types in which private partners assume more responsibilities (Percoco, 2014), and that a sounder institutional environment moderates the negative effect of risk in PPPs' private investment (Wang et al., 2019). Other authors, such as Fleta-Asín and Muñoz (2020) find that PPPs' success in developing countries is more likely when institutional and economic environments are better. Private investors will be interested in engaging in projects with more likelihood of success. Therefore, host countries presenting sound institutional and environmental frameworks would be more attractive to private companies since the uncertainties surrounding the

projects and the transaction costs would be lower, boosting their participation in renewable energy PPPs. Thus, we pose the next research hypotheses:

RH7: A greater GDP positively impacts private participation in renewable energy PPPs.

RH8: A sounder institutional framework fosters the participation of private investors in renewable energy PPPs.

RH9: A sounder economic framework fosters the participation of private investors in renewable energy PPPs.

Beyond PPPs' features and host countries' environments, other stakeholders could affect the interest of private investors in renewable energy projects in developing countries (European Commission, 2004; Wang & Ma, 2020). This is the case for multilateral development banks (MDBs) (some examples are the World Bank, the Asian Development Bank, the Inter-American Development Bank, and the European Investment Bank or the West-African Development Bank, among others). These institutions play an important role in funding infrastructure projects in developing countries. From a broader point of view, the role of MDBs includes being a '*mechanism of credit enhancement and risk reduction, enabling the raising of private flows and helping governments to perform the necessary reforms*' (Basílio, 2014, p. 83). Marcelo [and House](#) (2016) find that MDBs' support positively affects the PPPs' infrastructural likelihood of success and Jandhyala (2016) obtains similar results. Thus, we pose the next research hypothesis:

RH10: The support of MDBs for renewable energy PPPs positively impacts the degree of participation of the private sector.

Finally, we want to determine in which countries MDBs' support is more necessary to attract private money flows to renewable energy PPPs. Basílio (2014) finds that the participation of MDBs in infrastructure projects is higher for poorer countries where institutional and economic frameworks suffer from important weaknesses. Jandhyala (2016) shows that the impact of MDBs' support on PPPs' success is greater when the project is deployed in weaker institutional frameworks. When economic and institutional conditions in the PPPs' host country are well established, the uncertainties surrounding projects diminish, and it becomes more attractive for private investors to invest there and the MDBs' support becomes less

critical for achieving the involvement of private companies. However, in more deteriorated environments in which private investors are more reluctant to invest, the support of MDBs could mitigate the repellent effect of institutional and economic weaknesses. Thus, we pose the next research hypotheses:

RH11: The support of MDBs for renewable energy PPPs is more relevant in attracting private investors when projects are deployed in countries with weaker economic and institutional frameworks.

Figure 1 plots the research hypotheses tested in this research.

Insert Figure 1

3. Data and Methods

3.1. Data

The sample contains 1,371 PPPs in renewable energies. The PPPs information comes from the Private Participation in Infrastructure World Bank Database (WBPD)⁵. To define the sample, we select all the PPPs from the electricity subsector related with one of the next technologies: enhanced geothermal (19 PPPs), large hydro (>50 MW) (253 PPPs), small hydro (<50 MW) (264 PPPs), wind (435 PPPs), solar photovoltaic (PV) (228 PPPs), concentrated solar power (CSP) (13 PPPs), waste (75 PPPs) and biomass (84 PPPs). The PPPs were deployed in 63 developing countries during the period from 1997 to 2016. Figure 2 plots the distribution of projects across countries.

Insert Figure 2

Our dependent variable is the degree of private involvement in PPPs in renewable energies (PRIV_PART). To measure it, in line the previous literature, we use the percentage of Special Purpose Vehicles (SPV) owned by private sponsors (*private percentage*). As Wang et al. (2019) explain (p. 121) ‘An SPV is a legal entity created for narrow, specific or temporary objectives. A higher percentage of the SPV owned by private sponsors means higher degrees of private investment’. This variable can adopt values in the range of 0%–100%.

⁵ This database is publicly available at <https://ppi.worldbank.org/en/ppi>

The variables at the project level include the size, age, and type of PPP, the contract award method, the prime revenue source, and the presence of private local sponsors. The SIZE of the project is approached by the logarithm of the total investment in millions of US dollars. The AGE of the project is computed as the difference between the year when the PPP was initiated and the last year with information for this project in the WBPD database. The PPPs included in our sample match with one of the next types defined by the World Bank: Management and Lease contracts, Brownfields, and Greenfields. These types are ordered from more responsibilities retained by the public sector to more responsibilities assumed by the private partner. We create an indicator variable (TYPE) adopting values in the range 1–3, representing each value of the three different types of PPPs, and with 1 to 3, less to more, representing responsibilities assumed by the private sector⁶. Regarding the contract award method, we create a dummy variable (COMP) that adopts the value of 1 when the contract award method is competitive, and 0 otherwise. For the prime revenue source, we create a dummy variable (MARKET) taking the value of 1 when the prime revenue source of the PPP is the sale of electricity to the market (both retail and wholesale) and 0 otherwise. Finally, we create a dummy variable (LOCAL) adopting the value of 1 when local sponsors participate in the PPP and 0 otherwise.

At the country level, we consider the country size approached by the log of GDP for each country where the PPP is deployed (GDP)⁷. To measure the quality of the institutional environment, we use the World Bank’s Worldwide Governance Indicators database (WGI)⁸. This set of governance indicators have been used in PPP previous literature—see among others, Percoco (2014), Wang et al. (2019), or Fleta-Asín and Muñoz (2020) and cover six dimensions: voice and accountability (VA), political stability and absence of violence (PS), government effectiveness (GE), regulatory quality (RQ), rule of law (RL), and control of corruption (CC). These indicators are highly correlated and cannot be used all together in the

⁶ A similar approach has been used by previous literature—see among others, Percoco (2014), Wang et al. (2018), Wang et al. (2019), or Fleta-Asín and Muñoz (2020).

⁷ Alternatively, we have used the log of population as a proxy of country size. For the sake of brevity, we do not report these results but they are available upon request.

⁸ This database is publicly available at <https://info.worldbank.org/governance/wgi/>

same model to avoid potential multicollinearity problems. Thus, we include them one by one in the models. Furthermore, to measure the quality of the institutional environment from an overall point of view and following previous literature (Fleta-Asín & Muñoz, 2020), we build a variable which is the average of the six indicators (G). To measure the economic environment, we use the index of economic freedom from the Heritage Foundation⁹ (EFI). We believe that this index measures the economic environment of a country in terms of whether it enables or hinders economic activity and businesses. In addition, we consider three more specific additional indicators related to the openness of the market (trade freedom [TF], investment freedom [IF], and financial freedom [FF]). Previous literature on PPPs has also used Heritage Foundation indicators (Fleta-Asín et al., 2020). Following prior literature (Fleta-Asín et al., 2020; Fleta-Asín & Muñoz, 2020), we consider all the variables at the country level according to the year before the PPP was deployed.

The multilateral development banks' support is approached by a dummy variable (MDB) adopting the value of 1 when one or several MDBs support the PPPs and 0 otherwise (see among others, Basílio, 2014). This information is obtained from the WBPD database.

Finally, we include across models some additional dummy variables as controls. First, we include several dummies to control for the period in which the PPP was deployed. More specifically, we split the full sample (1997–2016) into four symmetric cohorts of five years and include three dummy variables D97_01/D02_06/D07_11 adopting the value of 1 when the project is set out in the periods 1997–2001, 2002–2006, 2007–2011, or otherwise 0 (we take the period 2012–2016 as the base category to avoid multicollinearity). We also include dummy variables to control for the specific renewable energy technology. In particular, we include the following dummy variables: D_Geo, D_Large_Hydro, D_Small_Hydro, D_Waste, D_Wind, D_Biomass, and D_SolarPV, adopting the value of 1 when the PPPs refer to these technologies and 0 otherwise (we take concentrated solar power as the base category to avoid multicollinearity). In addition, we control for the continent in which the PPP is deployed. Thus, we include three dummy variables, D_Africa, D_America, and D_Asia that adopt the value of 1 when the project is launched in those continents and 0

⁹ These indicators are publicly available at <https://www.heritage.org/index/about>

otherwise (Europe is the base category to avoid multicollinearity). All these dummy variables allow us to control our empirical evidence for the specificities that could show different periods, renewable energy technologies, and geographical areas making our empirical evidence more robust.

Table 1 provides summary statistics for all these variables and tables 2 and 3 provide the pairwise correlation matrix. [In addition, a summary table of the variables, their definition, and source is included in the Annex \(see Table 8\).](#)

Insert Tables 1, 2, and 3

3.2. Methods

Tobit models to estimate percentages of capital are usual in the literature (Chan & Makino, 2007; Han et al., 1999). Specifically, the most recent investigations of PPPs that estimate the same dependent variable and with the same database use this technique (Wang et al., 2019, 2019b).

Thus, since our dependent variable (PRIV_PART) only can adopt values between 0% and 100%, and because we consider that the excess of frequencies in one value (e.g. 100% of ownership in our case) represent the real choice of the private investors investigated with an absence of missing values (Amore & Murtinu, 2019), the proper statistical estimation technique is a Tobit or censored regression model which makes a linear regression in which the dependent variable is censored. In our case, the dependent variable is censored in its lower limit at 0 and in its upper limit at 1 (Wang et al., 2019). First, we test the RHs from 1 to 6 related to variables at the project level. Thus, we regress the dependent variable on controls and project variables (model 1).

$$\begin{aligned}
 PRIV_PART_i = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 D97_01 + \beta_2 D92_06 + \beta_3 D07_11 + \beta_4 D_Africa + \beta_5 D_America + \\
 & \beta_6 D_Asia + \beta_7 D_Geo + \beta_8 D_Large_hydro + \beta_9 D_Small_hydro + \beta_{10} D_Waste + \\
 & \beta_{11} D_Wind + \beta_{12} D_Biomass + \beta_{13} D_Solar_PV + \beta_{14} SIZE + \beta_{15} AGE + \beta_{16} TYPE + \\
 & \beta_{17} COMP + \beta_{18} MARKET + \beta_{19} LOCAL + u_i
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{model 1}$$

Secondly, to contrast RH7, we add to model 1 the log_GDP (model 2).

$$PRIV_PART_i = Model\ 1 + \beta_{20} GDP + u_i
 \tag{model 2}$$

In third place, to test RH8, we add to model 2 the WGI (model 3). Since these indicators can be decomposed, we also aggregate them separately to model 2 to avoid multicollinearity problems following previous literature (see among others, Percoco, 2014, or Fleta-Asín & Muñoz, 2020).

$$PRIV_PART_i = Model\ 2 + \beta_{21}WGI + u_i \quad (\text{model 3})$$

In fourth place, to test RH9, we add to model 2 the indicators from the Heritage Foundation (model 4). We also add these indicators to model 2 and separately, in order to avoid multicollinearity problems with WGI and the Heritage Foundation ones respectively.

$$PRIV_PART_i = Model\ 2 + \beta_{21}Heritage + u_i \quad (\text{model 4})$$

Finally, we add to models 3 and 4 the variable approaching the multilateral development banks' support (RH10) and, in turn, we add to these models the interaction term between this variable and the proxies of the institutional and economic environments (RH11). In the models in which we include interactions, we use centred variables to avoid multicollinearity problems.

$$PRIV_PART_i = Model\ 3 + \beta_{21}G + \beta_{22}MDBs + u_i \quad (\text{model 5})$$

$$PRIV_PART_i = Model\ 3 + \beta_{21}EFI + \beta_{22}MDBs + u_i \quad (\text{model 6})$$

$$PRIV_PART_i = Model\ 3 + \beta_{21}G + \beta_{22}MDBs + \beta_{23}MDBs * G + u_i \quad (\text{model 7})$$

$$PRIV_PART_i = Model\ 3 + \beta_{21}EFI + \beta_{22}MDBs + \beta_{23}MDBs * EFI + u_i \quad (\text{model 8})$$

4. Empirical findings and discussion

Table 4 reports the results from models 1, 2, and 3 (model 3 when considering the average of the six WGI (G)), that allow us to test RH1-RH8.

Insert Table 4

Focussing on model 1, we can observe that the estimated coefficient on SIZE is negative and significant. This means that the size of the project could prevent private investors from being involved in renewable energy PPPs. This result leads us to not reject the RH1. The reason behind this inverse relationship could be that larger projects are more complex to manage and involve higher transaction costs. Jimenez et al. (2017) find that the size of the project

negatively affects the likelihood of success because of the management complexity of larger projects. Brown and Potoski (2003) explain that transaction costs determine the mechanism selected by governments to deliver services to citizens. More specifically, these authors maintain that more complex services, involving high asset-specific investments, raise the likelihood that governments deliver these services by their own means instead of contracting out to private companies. Leigland (2018) explains the reasons behind the complexity of larger projects, such as the share of multiple stakeholders, harder and longer negotiations, or longer contract periods being more likely to lead to the materialisation of unforeseen issues. Similarly, Ansar et al. (2016) point out that larger PPPs are more vulnerable to unforeseen events. Flyvbjerg (2014) provides evidence showing that 90 percent of projects costing over one billion dollars suffer cost overruns and delays and indicates that (p. 20) '*Private capital is no panacea for the ills in megaproject management, to be sure; in some cases, private capital may even make things worse...*'. Thus, public authorities should carefully define the size of the renewable energy projects in order to attract private investors. Further research could shed light on the optimum size of these projects by performing more specific analyses on this issue.

The estimated coefficient on AGE is negative and significant. This means that private participation in renewable energy PPPs set out in recent years is greater than in projects deployed earlier. This result supports the RH2. The reasons for this empirical evidence can be diverse. First, technological evolution can play an important role in the profitability of renewable energies (see among others, Zhang et al., 2013). Secondly, pro-environmental legislation and tax incentives are also important drivers of renewable energy profitability (Talavera et al., 2016). This type of law and fiscal policies are gaining momentum in developing countries, in part, because they could constitute a useful tool to mitigate the increasing impact of global warming in these areas (Cottrell & Falcao, 2018). Thus, our results reflect that the interest of private investors in engaging in renewable energy PPP projects in developing countries has increased over time.

The estimated coefficient on TYPE is positive and significant. This means that the more responsibilities assumed by the private investor, the more the involvement of the private partner in the PPP. This result leads us to not reject RH3. This result is not striking and aligns

with that obtained previously by Wang et al. (2018) in a sample of Chinese PPPs. As these authors explain, when private investors retain more residual rights over the assets involved in the service delivery, they have greater incentives to invest more in the project. Private investors owning more residual rights over the assets can operate them for a longer period and in an advantageous position (Zhang, 2014). Thus, the public sector aiming to attract private money for funding electricity services' expansion should promote PPP types where private investors take more responsibilities (for example, Greenfields versus Management and Lease contracts or Brownfields).

The estimated coefficient on COMP is negative and non-significant. This result leads us to reject RH4. This means that the contract award method does not impact the degree of private investor participation in renewable energy PPPs, at least for the sample analysed. This evidence is not aligned to that obtained by previous literature on PPPs, such as Wang et al. (2018) who observe a positive and significant relationship between competitive award methods and private participation because of the efficiency gains achieved from the tendering process. This could be due to the fact that competitive award procedures raise efficiency but also can reduce profitability because of the competition among private agents. The estimated coefficient on MARKET is positive and significant, leading us to not reject the RH5. When the prime revenue source depends on the sales to electricity consumers, private investors have more incentives to be efficient and competitive. Thus, we detect the positive effect of efficiency gains in private investors' attraction through the method of generating revenues. Together these last two results suggest that *ex-ante* incentives for gaining efficiency (a competitive award method) could be less relevant when setting *ex-post* incentives for gaining efficiency (market discipline in the achievement of revenues). The estimated coefficient on LOCAL is positive but non-significant. This leads us to reject the RH6. Previous literature has shown that the presence of local sponsors positively affects the PPPs' success (see among others, Fleta-Asín & Muñoz, 2020). However, our results reveal that the presence of private local sponsors does not impact the attraction of private investment to renewable energy PPPs.

Model 2 adds to model 1 the log of GDP and allows us to test the RH7. The estimated coefficient on the log of GDP is negative and significant, this result being contrary to our expectations and leading us to reject RH7. This means that the involvement of private

investors in renewable energy PPPs is greater in countries with lower GDPs. This finding could reflect that low GDP countries can suffer from greater budgetary constraints when funding the expansion of the electricity services' delivery making the involvement of private investors more necessary. When analysing in detail the distribution of the different types of PPPs' contracts across countries in our sample, we observe that most PPPs have management and lease contracts (in which the public party retains ownership of the facility) or Brownfield projects (those in which the private party does not take the responsibility for building a new facility but refurbishes, improves, or expands an existing public asset) and are deployed in high GDP countries such as Brazil, China, the Russian Federation, or Turkey among others. In low GDP countries, the lack of facilities' endowment and the limited capacity of their governments to finance with public money the provision of these infrastructures make the involvement of private companies more necessary, not only to operate renewable energy plants built and owned by the public sector but also to build these facilities.

Model 3 allows us to analyse the impact of the institutional environment in private investment in renewable energy PPPs. To approach the quality of the institutional framework where the project is deployed, we use the WGI that cover six dimensions. These indicators are highly correlated among them and cannot be considered altogether in the same model since it would lead to multicollinearity problems. Thus, first, to analyse the impact of the overall institutional environment, we add to model 3 the average of the six indicators (Fleta-Asín & Muñoz, 2020). As can be seen, the estimated coefficient on G is positive and significant, meaning that a better institutional environment attracts private investment to renewable energy PPPs. This result aligns with the empirical evidence obtained previously for other infrastructures—see among others, Percoco (2014), Panayides et al. (2015), or Wang et al. (2019). As North (1991, p. 97) explains institutions *'define the choice set and therefore determine transaction and production costs and hence the profitability and feasibility of engaging in economic activity'*. Besides, institutions could have a special impact in developing countries since the public sector usually exerts a greater influence on market transactions in these countries than in the developed ones (Hoffman et al., 2016). Institutions diminish the uncertainty surrounding the transactions (North, 1991) and facilitate the formation of expectations regarding economic agents' behaviour (Scott, 1995). Fleta-Asín

and Muñoz (2020) find that a sounder institutional environment positively impacts the likelihood of PPPs' success.

Regarding the control variables, their sign and significance are consistent across models (see Table 4). Thus, the temporary cohorts are not significant, so the investment period would not be affecting the results. On the other hand, the variables that control the regions are negative and significant in Africa, America, and Asia when compared with their base category, so that private participation in these regions would be negative compared to those carried out in Europe. This could be because their economic structures do not allow easy integration of private investors. Finally, there is a significantly greater private participation in the waste and wind technologies, which could be due to the expected safety and/or profitability of these activities.

In Table 5, we report the results from model 3 but considering each one of the six dimensions covered by the WGI to perform a more detailed analysis of the institutional factors.

Insert Table 5

For five out of six dimensions, the estimated coefficients are positive and significant. In model 3.a., the voice and accountability indicator (VA)¹⁰ referred to the '*extent to which a country's citizens are able to participate in selecting their government, as well as freedom of expression, freedom of association, and a free media*'. It also reflects whether citizens can monitor the actions of governments. Thus, good records on this indicator reflect a more transparent government. Transparency in the public sector allows private investors to better anticipate its behaviour, enabling the building of trusty relationships between the public and private partners, and leading the private party to be willing to take more responsibilities in PPPs. Trust could be a key aspect in dealing with unforeseen events non-reflected into incomplete contracts (English & Baxter, 2010) diminishing uncertainty and transaction costs. In this way, Soliño and Santos (2016) and Wang et al. (2018) identify transparency as an important factor for attracting private investment.

In models 3.c, 3.d, and 3.e we consider the government effectiveness (GE), the regulatory quality (RQ), and the rule of law (RL) indicators, respectively. GE is referred to as '*the*

¹⁰ The definitions of the WGI have been extracted from Kaufmann et al. (2009, p. 6).

quality of public services, the quality of the civil service and the degree of its independence from political pressures, the quality of policy formulation and implementation, and the credibility of the government's commitment to such policies'. RQ is *'the ability of the government to formulate and implement sound policies and regulations that permit and promote private sector development'*; and rule of law refers to *'the extent to which agents have confidence in and abide by the rules of society, and in particular the quality of contract enforcement, property rights, the police, and the courts, as well as the likelihood of crime and violence'*. Again, good records on all these governance indicators would diminish the uncertainty surrounding the transaction and would encourage private investments. Practitioners and academics identify the expropriation or the nationalisation of assets and the poor public decision-making process as critical risk factors hindering the involvement of private investors in PPPs (Bing et al. 2005). Government efficiency and commitment significantly diminish the likelihood of these risks materialising. RQ and RL are found by Percoco (2014) to be especially relevant in attracting private investment to transport infrastructures. One aspect that could be a determinant to encourage private involvement in renewable energies could be the stability of the legislation and regulation ruling them. For example, Talavera et al. (2016) explain how regulatory changes in Spain have caused solar photovoltaic to turn very rapidly from a prosperous business into an unstable sector. Legislation change, change in tax regulation, or industrial regulatory change, are critical risk factors identified by academics and practitioners involved in PPP agreements (Bing et al., 2005). The stability of the regulatory framework would provide confidence and certainties to private investors that could encourage their participation in renewable energy PPPs. Baker (2016) also identifies the regulatory quality and the rule of law as key factors for attracting private investment to PPPs in developing countries. All these variables become important since PPP contracts are incomplete and extend for longer periods. The existence of an independent judicial system guarantees that in case of conflict between the private and public partners the resolution of this conflict will not be partial, raising the confidence of private companies to invest.

In model 3.f, we analyse the control of corruption (CC) indicator. Corruption refers to *'the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain, including both petty and grand forms of corruption, as well as "capture" of the state by elites and private interests'*.

Corruption is a source of uncertainty, increases transaction costs, and negatively affects investment and growth (Méon & Weill, 2010). Corruption deviates the prices of goods from their marginal costs, jeopardising markets' efficiency (Zhao et al., 2003). Castro et al. (2014) observe that the PPPs' execution is less efficient when the project is deployed in environments marked by greater corruption. Jimenez et al. (2017) find that corruption negatively affects the likelihood of PPPs' success. Thus, corruption could discourage private companies from becoming involved in renewable energy PPPs.

Surprisingly, for one of the WGI, the estimated coefficient is negative and significant. This occurs when considering political stability and absence of violence (PS) (model 3.b.) referred to as *'the likelihood that the government will be destabilized or overthrown by unconstitutional or violent means, including politically-motivated violence and terrorism'*. This finding is striking since previous literature has observed that political stability is an important factor to attract private money (Morrissey & Udomkerdmongkol, 2012). However, most forms of violence come from inequalities, so an increase in these instabilities could provoke government responses that promote greater developments to favour the population in order to mitigate them. Londregan and Poole (1990) find that poverty is a common denominator in military *coups d'état* but at the same time, they do not obtain evidence that political instability impacts income growth. Feng (1997) also explains that political instability is a broad term referred to as multiple and different political changes, with the consequences of these changes being different economic growth. Thus, given all the institutional dimensions as a whole, we cannot reject RH8.

In Table 6, we analyse the impact of the economic environment on the attraction of private investors to renewable energy PPPs.

Insert Table 6

To test RH9, we add to model 2 the economic freedom index (EFI) from the Heritage Foundation (model 4) referred to as: *'In economically free societies, governments allow labor, capital, and goods to move freely, and refrain from coercion or constraint of liberty beyond the extent necessary to protect and maintain liberty itself'*¹¹. In addition, we also consider more specific indicators, also from the Heritage Foundation, reflecting the openness

¹¹ <https://www.heritage.org/index/about>

of the market. These indicators are trade freedom (TF) (model 4.a.) referred to as *'the extent of tariff and non-tariff barriers that affect imports and exports of goods and services'*; investment freedom (IF) (model 4.b.) referred to as *'constraints on the flow of investment capital. Individuals and firms would be allowed to move their resources into and out of specific activities, both internally and across the country's borders, without restrictions'*; and financial freedom (FF) (model 4.c.), referred to as *'banking efficiency as well as a measure of independence from government control and interference in the financial sector'*. As can be seen, the estimated coefficients are positive and significant meaning that a better economic environment attracts private investors to renewable energy PPPs. Thus, we cannot reject RH9. The economic environment could be an important source of relevant risk factors hindering the involvement of private investors with PPPs. Thus, practitioners and academics have identified poor financial markets, inflation rate volatility, interest rate volatility, or influential economic events (Bing et al., 2005) as relevant risk factors hindering the deployment of PPPs. Economic freedom has been identified as an important determinant of foreign direct investment inflows in Latin America (Bengoa & Sánchez-Robles, 2003) or East Asia (Quazi, 2007). Besides, Fleta-Asín and Muñoz (2020) find that a better economic environment impacts positively the likelihood of PPPs' success.

Finally, in Table 7 we report the results for testing RH10 and RH11.

Insert Table 7

Model 5/6 adds the MDBs' variable to model 3/4. As can be seen, in both models the estimated coefficient on this variable is positive and significant, meaning that those renewable energies PPPs supported by multilateral development banks attract more private investment. Thus, we cannot reject RH10. Multilateral development banks support infrastructure PPPs by providing funding, technical assistance, and by inducing developing countries to make the necessary reforms to succeed in their projects (Basílio, 2014). [Marcelo and House \(2016\)](#) or [Jandhyala \(2016\)](#) find that the likelihood of PPPs' success is greater when the project enjoys support from MDBs. Private investors could have a preference to engage in PPPs supported by this type of international institution. Models 7/8 adds to models 5/6 the interaction term between the MDBs variable and the institutional/economic environment proxy. Thus, these models allow us to test the RH11. The estimated coefficients on interaction terms, both in model 7 and 8, are negative and significant. This means that the

support of MDBs is revealed to be more relevant in attracting private investors when institutional and economic environments where the projects are deployed suffer from more weaknesses. These findings allow us to not reject RH11. Jandhyala (2016) finds that MDBs support impacts more on PPPs' failure likelihood when the PPPs' host countries are characterised by a more deteriorated institutional environment. Thus, the operational assistance of MDBs can help diminish the negative impact of some of the constraints arising from some institutional issues such as the lack of an independent judicial system or the existence of poor regulatory quality.

Finally, in order to check the robustness of the analysis, the same models were carried out using Tobit with robust estimators, obtaining the same signs and significance in all variables of the hypotheses. We also ran the same models considering the dependent variable as a fractional regression (Albalade et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2018), obtaining the same results related to the variables of the hypotheses with the sole exception of multilateral development banks dummy in model 8 that becomes non-significant. These unreported results are available upon request from the authors.

5. Conclusions, limitations, and avenues of further research

The implementation of measures to fight against global warming is urgent given the negative consequences of the temperature rise on society and the economy, especially in developing countries. Since an important part of the total worldwide GHG emissions proceeds from electricity production, an effective policy to curb global warming would be the promotion of renewable energies. PPPs constitute an important tool to foster renewable energies in developing countries, with the attraction of private investment being a key aspect. In this research, we analyse, for the first time, the determinants of private investment participation for a broad sample of PPPs in renewable energies (1,371 projects) from 63 developing countries, deployed in the period 1997–2016. Our findings show that PPPs which are smaller, younger, where the private partner takes more responsibilities, and the prime revenue source is the electricity consumers' payments, show a greater degree of private investors' participation. Regarding the institutional and economic frameworks where the project is deployed, our results indicate that stronger institutions and better economic conditions attract private investment. Thus, developing countries should make an effort to improve their

records in their governance indicators, especially in those related to government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law, control of corruption and transparency, and in their economic freedom indicators, in order to attract private investors to PPPs in renewable energies. Our findings also reveal that multilateral development banks' support positively impacts the attraction of private investors to renewable energy projects. In addition, these multilateral institutions should focus their support on projects deployed in countries presenting more institutional and economic weaknesses since, in these countries, this support has a larger impact on the attraction of private investors than in countries with sounder institutional and economic conditions.

Our research suffers from several limitations that could constitute avenues for further research. First, our data contains information at project and country levels but lacks information on private companies and public managers' characteristics. Further research could analyse how these characteristics affect the involvement of private investors in renewable energy PPPs. Moreover, our dataset is focussed on developing countries. However, the analyses of the determinants of private investment in renewable energy projects deployed in developed countries could be of interest, given the differences in terms of institutional and economic environments. Another avenue of further research could be the analyses of how specific pro-environmental legislation, tax incentives, or industry regulations impact PPPs in renewable energies. Finally, in this research, we focus on the determinants of private investment; however other issues are relevant such as the factors determining the success or failure of these projects, or factors affecting other performance measures such as delays or overruns.

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Figure 1: Research Hypotheses

Figure 2: Distribution of PPPs sample in renewable energy across countries

* The countries included in the research sample are: Albania, Algeria, Argentina, Armenia, Bangladesh, Belarus, Belize, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Brazil, Bulgaria, Cambodia, China, Colombia, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Egypt Arab Rep., El Salvador, Ethiopia, Gabon, Georgia, Ghana, Guatemala, Honduras, India, Indonesia, Jamaica, Jordan, Kenya, Kyrgyz Republic, Lao PDR, Macedonia FYR, Madagascar, Malaysia, Mauritius, Mexico, Mongolia, Montenegro, Morocco, Mozambique, Nepal, Nicaragua, Pakistan, Panama, Peru, Philippines, Romania, Russian Federation, Rwanda, Serbia, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Sri Lanka, Tajikistan, Tanzania, Thailand, Tonga, Turkey, Uganda, Ukraine, Vietnam, Zambia, and Zimbabwe.

Table 1: Summary Statistics*

	Obs.	Mean	SD	Min	Max
PRIV_PART	1,371	0.936	0.155	0.249	1
D97_01	1,371	0.033	0.178	0	1
D02_06	1,371	0.108	0.310	0	1
D07_11	1,371	0.351	0.477	0	1
D_Africa	1,371	0.066	0.249	0	1
D_America	1,371	0.333	0.472	0	1
D_Asia	1,371	0.513	0.500	0	1
D_Geo	1,371	0.014	0.117	0	1
D_Large_Hydro	1,371	0.185	0.388	0	1
D_Small_Hydro	1,371	0.193	0.394	0	1
D_Waste	1,371	0.055	0.227	0	1
D_Wind	1,371	0.317	0.466	0	1
D_Biomass	1,371	0.061	0.240	0	1
D_SolarPV	1,371	0.166	0.372	0	1
SIZE	1,371	4.144	1.355	-0.693	9.602
AGE	1,371	7.582	3.534	2	22
TYPE	1,371	2.910	0.303	1	3
COMP	1,371	0.257	0.437	0	1
MARKET	1,371	0.124	0.330	0	1
LOCAL	1,371	0.677	0.468	0	1
GDP	1,371	26.902	1.940	19.728	29.981
VA	1,371	-0.164	0.802	-1.749	1.111
PS	1,371	-0.091	0.321	-1.372	1.121
GE	1,371	-0.549	0.615	-2.810	1.072
RQ	1,371	-0.061	0.385	-1.935	0.940
RL	1,371	-0.266	0.346	-1.780	0.950
CC	1,371	-0.330	0.338	-1.402	0.786
G	1,371	-0.243	0.333	-1.483	0.823
EFI	1,371	57.525	5.344	22.1	76.9
TF	1,371	70.506	10.796	20	89.1
IF	1,371	44.468	15.620	0	90
FF	1,371	45.755	12.704	10	70
MDB	1,371	0.327	0.469	0	1

*The variables are defined in section 3.

Table 2: Correlation matrix (Part I)*

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
PRIV_PART																
D97_01	-0.15															
D02_06	-0.16	-0.06														
D07_11	-0.02	-0.14	-0.26													
D_Africa	-0.01	-0.02	-0.06	-0.12												
D_America	-0.14	0.11	0.09	0.00	-0.19											
D_Asia	0.07	-0.07	0.00	0.11	-0.27	-0.73										
D_Geo	0.04	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.04	-0.03	0.03									
D_Large_Hydro	-0.36	0.16	0.14	0.04	-0.09	0.26	-0.14	-0.06								
D_Small_Hydro	0.13	-0.04	0.13	0.12	-0.06	0.00	0.05	-0.06	-0.23							
D_Waste	0.02	0.08	0.11	0.02	0.00	0.05	0.00	-0.03	-0.11	-0.12						
D_Wind	0.02	-0.09	-0.12	-0.06	0.01	-0.06	-0.04	-0.08	-0.32	-0.33	-0.16					
D_Biomass	0.04	-0.05	-0.07	-0.02	-0.03	0.03	0.02	-0.03	-0.12	-0.12	-0.06	-0.17				
D_SolarPV	0.18	-0.08	-0.15	-0.08	0.10	-0.22	0.11	-0.05	-0.21	-0.22	-0.11	-0.30	-0.11			
SIZE	-0.14	0.00	-0.22	-0.07	0.15	0.13	-0.23	0.04	0.25	-0.40	-0.09	0.23	-0.08	-0.07		
AGE	-0.27	0.58	0.55	0.17	-0.11	0.12	0.00	0.14	0.26	0.15	0.14	-0.18	-0.09	-0.25	-0.18	
TYPE	0.27	-0.12	-0.10	-0.05	0.07	-0.27	0.18	-0.01	-0.49	0.03	0.06	0.20	0.08	0.13	0.12	-0.17
COMP	-0.20	0.03	0.02	-0.08	0.13	0.34	-0.31	-0.06	0.39	-0.15	-0.09	-0.10	-0.08	-0.03	0.13	-0.01
MARKET	0.10	-0.03	-0.05	0.00	-0.09	-0.09	-0.04	-0.03	0.07	-0.04	-0.05	0.12	-0.07	-0.09	0.03	-0.05
LOCAL	0.05	-0.10	0.07	0.05	-0.07	-0.14	0.30	-0.04	-0.15	0.14	0.10	-0.09	0.09	0.01	-0.21	0.01
GDP	-0.09	-0.07	-0.09	0.01	-0.19	0.15	0.12	-0.09	-0.05	-0.26	0.11	0.11	0.14	0.06	0.09	-0.16
VA	0.07	0.02	0.02	-0.04	0.10	0.48	-0.59	0.00	0.11	-0.05	-0.07	0.08	-0.11	-0.06	0.08	0.00
PS	0.05	0.01	-0.03	0.00	0.09	-0.05	0.08	-0.04	-0.12	-0.16	0.06	0.08	0.01	0.16	-0.01	-0.05
GE	-0.12	0.09	0.00	-0.07	0.12	0.38	-0.59	-0.08	0.12	-0.07	0.05	-0.01	0.02	-0.05	0.19	0.03
RQ	0.03	0.12	-0.04	-0.07	0.10	0.28	-0.48	-0.02	0.01	-0.11	0.00	0.09	-0.04	0.02	0.11	0.02
RL	0.09	0.02	-0.05	0.00	0.12	-0.03	-0.05	-0.10	-0.08	-0.06	-0.02	0.09	-0.02	0.07	-0.06	-0.06
CC	-0.05	0.08	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.41	-0.37	-0.10	0.09	-0.05	0.03	0.01	0.01	-0.05	0.02	0.09
G	0.01	0.08	0.00	-0.05	0.14	0.42	-0.57	-0.07	0.06	-0.11	0.00	0.08	-0.05	-0.01	0.10	0.01
EFI	0.13	0.06	0.03	-0.13	0.16	0.19	-0.37	0.02	0.00	-0.01	-0.05	0.06	-0.12	0.03	0.03	0.00
TF	0.24	-0.26	-0.39	0.04	0.08	-0.03	-0.24	0.03	-0.17	-0.07	-0.14	0.15	0.00	0.14	0.16	-0.47
IF	0.06	0.12	0.00	-0.14	0.09	0.37	-0.56	0.03	0.10	-0.04	-0.04	0.11	-0.13	-0.11	0.17	0.01
FF	0.09	0.09	-0.11	-0.17	0.23	0.35	-0.54	0.03	0.01	-0.04	-0.08	0.05	-0.07	0.04	0.12	-0.14
MDB	0.03	-0.02	0.03	0.09	0.03	-0.06	0.03	-0.04	0.05	0.07	-0.03	-0.07	0.07	-0.06	0.00	0.06

* The correlations significant at 10% are highlighted in bold.

Table 3: Correlation matrix (Part II)*

	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
TYPE	1.00															
COMP	-0.43	1.00														
MARKET	-0.17	0.07	1.00													
LOCAL	0.11	-0.11	0.05	1.00												
GDP	-0.12	0.13	-0.01	0.25	1.00											
VA	-0.15	0.31	0.18	-0.14	-0.03	1.00										
PS	-0.04	0.12	0.09	0.16	0.44	0.16	1.00									
GE	-0.12	0.15	0.04	-0.22	-0.03	0.14	0.13	1.00								
RQ	-0.14	0.19	0.26	-0.14	0.05	0.48	0.60	0.37	1.00							
RL	-0.05	0.16	0.22	0.05	0.19	0.54	0.65	0.13	0.56	1.00						
CC	-0.21	0.29	0.17	0.02	0.27	0.52	0.64	0.37	0.71	0.74	1.00					
G	-0.18	0.31	0.21	-0.11	0.14	0.75	0.60	0.54	0.81	0.77	0.86	1.00				
EFI	-0.06	0.13	0.22	-0.20	-0.30	0.46	0.40	0.16	0.78	0.45	0.50	0.61	1.00			
TF	0.04	-0.02	0.22	-0.13	-0.16	0.07	0.18	0.19	0.47	0.09	0.18	0.25	0.47	1.00		
IF	-0.13	0.19	0.31	-0.29	-0.25	0.57	0.15	0.26	0.71	0.36	0.46	0.61	0.77	0.35	1.00	
FF	-0.09	0.22	0.12	-0.20	-0.20	0.56	0.26	0.18	0.70	0.35	0.42	0.59	0.79	0.40	0.70	1.00
MDB	-0.01	-0.04	0.03	0.04	-0.03	-0.07	-0.02	0.07	-0.05	-0.02	-0.02	-0.03	-0.05	-0.02	-0.04	-0.09

* The correlations significant at 10% are highlighted in bold.

Table 4: Empirical Findings RH1-8

	Model 1: RH1-6	Model 2: RH7	Model 3: RH8_G
SIZE (RH1)	-0.046*** (0.018)	-0.041** (0.018)	-0.037** (0.018)
AGE (RH2)	-0.040*** (0.013)	-0.042*** (0.013)	-0.041*** (0.013)
TYPE (RH3)	0.328*** (0.069)	0.281*** (0.071)	0.259*** (0.071)
COMP (RH4)	-0.035 (0.053)	-0.012 (0.053)	-0.043 (0.053)
MARKET (RH5)	0.352*** (0.077)	0.343*** (0.076)	0.299*** (0.077)
LOCAL (RH6)	0.003 (0.042)	0.032 (0.044)	0.027 (0.043)
GDP (RH7)		-0.031** (0.013)	-0.046*** (0.013)
G (RH8)			0.295*** (0.079)
D97_01	0.222 (0.200)	0.247 (0.199)	0.183 (0.197)
D02_06	-0.030 (0.122)	-0.020 (0.121)	-0.043 (0.119)
D07_11	0.009 (0.066)	0.021 (0.066)	0.007 (0.065)
D_Africa	-0.540*** (0.163)	-0.561*** (0.164)	-0.565*** (0.163)
D_America	-0.352** (0.148)	-0.290* (0.151)	-0.304** (0.153)
D_Asia	-0.386*** (0.148)	-0.339** (0.150)	-0.227 (0.154)
D_Geo	0.727*** (0.255)	0.665*** (0.253)	0.755*** (0.252)
D_Large_Hydro	-0.013 (0.154)	-0.067 (0.155)	-0.015 (0.153)
D_Small_Hydro	0.481*** (0.166)	0.432*** (0.166)	0.468*** (0.163)
D_Waste	0.308* (0.171)	0.311* (0.170)	0.357** (0.167)
D_Wind	0.217 (0.153)	0.220 (0.152)	0.265* (0.150)
D_Biomass	0.255 (0.171)	0.259 (0.170)	0.309* (0.167)
D_SolarPV	0.806*** (0.189)	0.814*** (0.188)	0.828*** (0.185)
Intercept	1.056*** (0.283)	1.972*** (0.466)	2.407*** (0.481)
N	1,371	1,371	1,371
LR- χ^2	411.04***	417.34***	431.72***
Log-Likelihood	-407.97	-404.83	-397.64
McFadden's pseudo R ²	0.3350	0.3401	0.3518

Notes: Standard errors are in parentheses. ***Significant at 1%; **Significant at 5%; *Significant at 10%.

Table 5: Empirical Findings RH8 (WGI dimensions)

	Model 3.a: RH8_VA	Model 3.b: RH8_PS	Model 3.c: RH8_GE	Model 3.d: RH8_RQ	Model 3.e: RH8_RL	Model 3.f: RH8_CC
VA	0.189*** (0.032)					
PS		-0.157*** (0.04)				
GE			0.348*** (0.079)			
RQ				0.244*** (0.069)		
RL					0.193*** (0.064)	
CC						0.209*** (0.079)
SIZE	-0.033* (0.018)	-0.037** (0.018)	-0.036** (0.018)	-0.040** (0.018)	-0.036** (0.018)	-0.038** (0.018)
AGE	-0.038*** (0.013)	-0.041*** (0.013)	-0.043*** (0.013)	-0.043*** (0.013)	-0.039*** (0.013)	-0.045*** (0.013)
TYPE	0.240*** (0.069)	0.279*** (0.071)	0.264*** (0.071)	0.274*** (0.071)	0.263*** (0.071)	0.267*** (0.071)
COMP	-0.061 (0.052)	-0.016 (0.053)	-0.040 (0.053)	-0.036 (0.054)	-0.041 (0.054)	-0.035 (0.054)
MARKET	0.281*** (0.076)	0.340*** (0.076)	0.308*** (0.077)	0.305*** (0.078)	0.313*** (0.077)	0.310*** (0.078)
LOCAL	0.009 (0.043)	0.019 (0.044)	0.028 (0.043)	0.029 (0.043)	0.026 (0.043)	0.024 (0.044)
GDP	-0.028** (0.012)	-0.029** (0.012)	-0.066*** (0.015)	-0.044*** (0.013)	-0.042*** (0.013)	-0.046*** (0.014)
Intercept	1.860***(0.453)	1.873***(0.462)	2.957***(0.525)	2.279*** (0.478)	2.311*** (0.479)	2.498*** (0.513)
Time controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Continent controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Technology controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	1,371	1,371	1,371	1,371	1,371	1,371
LR- χ^2	454.92***	433.43***	438.12***	430.52***	426.77***	424.6***
Log-Likelihood	-386.03	-396.78	-394.44	-398.24	-400.11	-401.20
McFadden's pseudo R ²	0.3708	0.3532	0.3571	0.3509	0.3478	0.346

Notes: Standard errors are in parentheses. ***Significant at 1%; **Significant at 5%; *Significant at 10%.

Table 6: Empirical Findings RH9 (Economic Environment)

	Model 4: RH9_EFI	Model 4.a: RH9_TF	Model 4.b: RH9_IF	Model 4.c: RH9_FF
EFI	0.023*** (0.004)			
TF		0.007*** (0.002)		
IF			0.009*** (0.002)	
FF				0.008*** (0.002)
SIZE	-0.032* (0.018)	-0.044** (0.018)	-0.045*** (0.018)	-0.038** (0.018)
AGE	-0.043*** (0.013)	-0.035*** (0.013)	-0.041*** (0.013)	-0.036*** (0.013)
TYPE	0.253*** (0.071)	0.306*** (0.072)	0.262*** (0.072)	0.272*** (0.071)
COMP	-0.041 (0.053)	-0.008 (0.053)	-0.037 (0.053)	-0.037 (0.053)
MARKET	0.292*** (0.077)	0.323*** (0.077)	0.263*** (0.078)	0.313*** (0.077)
LOCAL	0.033 (0.043)	0.024 (0.043)	0.051 (0.043)	0.032 (0.043)
GDP	-0.021* (0.012)	-0.023* (0.013)	-0.024* (0.012)	-0.028** (0.012)
Intercept	0.396 (0.537)	1.094** (0.530)	1.354*** (0.472)	1.445*** (0.479)
Time controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Continent controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Technology controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	1,371	1,371	1,371	1,371
LR- χ^2	445.6***	428.63***	443.29***	431.99***
Log-Likelihood	-390.69	-399.18	-391.85	-397.50
McFadden's pseudo R ²	0.3632	0.3493	0.3613	0.3521

Notes: Standard errors are in parentheses. ***Significant at 1%; **Significant at 5%; *Significant at 10%.

Table 7: Empirical Findings RH10-11 (Multilateral Development Banks)

	Model 5: RH10	Model 6: RH10	Model 7: RH11	Model 8: RH11
MDBs (RH10)	0.089** (0.041)	0.089** (0.041)	0.086** (0.041)	0.069* (0.041)
G	0.293*** (0.079)		0.437*** (0.090)	
EFI		0.023*** (0.004)		0.033*** (0.006)
MDBs*G (RH11)			-0.404*** (0.114)	
MDBs*EFI (RH11)				-0.023*** (0.008)
SIZE	-0.039** (0.018)	-0.033* (0.018)	-0.041** (0.018)	-0.032* (0.018)
AGE	-0.040*** (0.013)	-0.042*** (0.013)	-0.039*** (0.013)	-0.041*** (0.013)
TYPE	0.257*** (0.071)	0.250*** (0.071)	0.261*** (0.070)	0.252*** (0.071)
COMP	-0.042 (0.053)	-0.039 (0.053)	-0.048 (0.053)	-0.046 (0.053)
MARKET	0.299*** (0.077)	0.293*** (0.077)	0.292*** (0.077)	0.287*** (0.077)
LOCAL	0.015 (0.043)	0.021 (0.043)	0.033 (0.043)	0.029 (0.043)
GDP	-0.044*** (0.013)	-0.020 (0.012)	-0.044*** (0.013)	-0.017 (0.012)
Intercept	2.356*** (0.480)	0.348 (0.535)	2.303*** (0.474)	1.631*** (0.458)
Time controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Continent controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Technology controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	1,371	1,371	1,371	1,371
LR- χ^2	436.54***	450.54***	449.54***	459.13***
Log-Likelihood	-395.23	-388.22	-388.72	-383.93
McFadden's pseudo R ²	0.3558	0.3672	0.3664	0.3742

Notes: Standard errors are in parentheses. ***Significant at 1%; **Significant at 5%; *Significant at 10%.

Annex

Table 8: Summary of variables

Variable	Definition	Source
PRIV_PART	Percentage of Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) owned by private sponsors.	The Private Participation in Infrastructure World Bank Database (WBPD).
SIZE	The size of the project is approached by the logarithm of the total investment in millions of US dollars.	
AGE	The age of the project is computed as the difference between the year when the PPP was set out and the last year with information for this project in the WBPD database.	
TYPE	Indicator variable adopting values in the range 1-3, representing each value the three different types of PPPs (<i>Management and Lease contracts, Brownfields, and Greenfields</i>) and being 1 to 3, less to more, responsibilities assumed by the private sector.	
COMP	A dummy variable that adopts the value of 1 when the contract award method is competitive and 0 otherwise.	
MARKET	A dummy variable taking the value of 1 when the prime revenue source of the PPP is the sale of electricity to the market (both retail and wholesale) and 0 otherwise.	
LOCAL	A dummy variable adopting the value of 1 when local sponsors participate in the PPP and 0 otherwise.	
D97_01/D02_06/D07_011	A dummy variable adopting the value of 1 when the PPP is deployed in the period 1997-2001/2002-2006/2007-2011 respectively, and 0 otherwise.	
D_Africa/D_America/D_Asia	A dummy variable adopting the value of 1 when the PPP is deployed in Africa/America/Asia and 0 otherwise.	
D_Geo/D_Large_Hydro/D_Small_Hydro /D_Waste/D_Wind/D_Biomass /D_SolarPV	A dummy variable adopting the value of 1 when the PPPs refer to enhanced geothermal/large hydrothermal/small hydrothermal/waste-to-energy/wind/biomass/solar photovoltaic, technologies respectively and 0 otherwise.	
GDP	The log of GDP for each country where the PPP is deployed.	The World Bank.
VA/PS/GE/RQ/RL/CC	Voice and Accountability / Political Stability / Government Effectiveness / Regulatory Quality / Rule of Law / Control of Corruption Worldwide Governance Indicators.	The World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators database (WGI).
G	Average of VA, PS, GE, RQ, CC.	
EFI	Index of Economic Freedom.	
TF /IF / FF	Trade / Investment /Finance Freedom Index.	The Heritage Foundation.
MDBs	A dummy variable adopting the value of 1 when one or several Multilateral Development Banks support the PPPs and 0 otherwise.	The Private Participation in Infrastructure World Bank Database (WBPD).